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Review Article

Healthy Drink with Butterfly Pea for Gut Health, Boosted Immunity, And Enhanced Mental Clarity (reduce stress)

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ABSTRACT

A drink that is healthy and contains a herbal treatment that has been traditionally used to improve immunity, improve digestive health, and improve mental clarity. This abstract explains the characteristics of the "healthy drink," how it affects butterfly pea and black tea, and the purported health advantages. The available scientific data supporting these benefits is also covered. Formulation, chemical makeup, and probable uses in medicine The nutritional potential of the drink and the phytoconstituents it contains are covered in this abstract. Additionally, it highlights the encouraging outcomes of in vitro and in vivo research on fermented beverages. This abstract addresses several aspects of drink, such as how it is made, what makes it up chemically and microbiologically, and what makes SCOBYs what they are. It also covers the laws that control the manufacture and promotion of healthy beverages as well as their potential advantages. Current trends in healthful beverages: traditional and non-traditional The creation of beverages utilizing various substrates and fermentation enhancers is covered in this abstract. It also goes over the traditional and non-conventional fermentation techniques that have been applied to create healthy beverages. Including its manufacturing specifications and its uses in many industrial domains. It also covers the impact of its consumption on human health.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays people are increasingly concerned about their own health. People want to become healthier, and the adoption of healthier lifestyles is necessary to improve quality of life and to reduce the numerous pathologies and comorbidities associated with nutrient inadequacy or poor diet

choices [6,1]. People are concerned about their body, their mind and their health, and so their search for healthy foods or specific foods that improve health, such as functional foods, has been increasing [7,8,9]

Gut health:

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Refers to the balance and well-being of the microorganisms living in the gastrointestinal tract (GI tract), also known as the gut microbiome. The gut microbiome plays a crucial role in maintaining overall physical and mental health.[1]

1. Digestive issues
2. Immune system function
3. Autoimmune diseases
3. Mental health disorders
4. Chronic inflammation
5. Impaired immune function

Anxiety:

Anxiety is a feeling of worry, nervousness, or fear that is persistent and overwhelming. It can interfere with a person's daily life, relationships, and overall well-being. Common symptoms of anxiety include: [4,5]

1. Restlessness and irritability
2. Difficulty concentration
3. Sleep disturbances.
4. Rapid heartbeat and palpitation
5. Sweating and trembling.
6. Fear or avoidance of certain situation

Depression:

Depression is a type of mental disorder marked by a lingering sense of hopelessness, melancholy, and disinterest in activities. It can have an impact on a person's ideas, emotions, and behaviours, making day-to-day functioning challenging. Typical signs of depression consist of: [4,5].

1. A chronic sense of despair and pessimism
2. A decline in interest in pursuits
3. Modifications to sleep and eating habits
5. Weariness and low vitality
5. Difficulty focusing and making choices
7. Guilt, worthlessness, and powerlessness feelings.

Benefits of Healthy drink

- Potential Benefits
- enhance gut health
- ease pain and migraine
- accelerates ulcer healing
- enhance digestion and bowel function
- increase vitality For so many of the ailments of our day, such a significant advantage.

The body sends out stress signals that suggest imminent failure when it experiences systemic or intestinal abnormalities. These indications are signs of an illness. Drink doesn't have the same purpose as over-the-counter or prescription drugs. [1, 3]

• Five ways that drinking reduces stress:

- Adrenaline and cortisol are released to speed up heart rate, arouse senses, and prime muscles for rapid action.

1. Beverages are adaptogen.

An adaptogen is defined as a drug, usually a herb that by restoring physiological function and reducing stress response, improves the body's capability to withstand stressors, boost vitality, and improve work capacity and concentration.

2. Drink serves as a stabilizing a healthy digestive system.

Improved digestion and acidity can help with ulcers and irritable bowel syndrome, two common gut manifestations of stress.

3. Has vitamin C and B vitamins.

The presence of vitamin B6 and B12, often known as thiamine, in this product is proven to aid the body combat depression, balance mood, and enhance concentration. Includes vitamin C as well, which inhibits the release of cortisol, one of the stress hormones. Elevations of cortisol in the blood can lead to depression, hypertension, and difficulty thinking clearly.

4. Drinking can lower sugar and caffeine intake.

Tea's L-theanine balances the negative effects of caffeine, giving you calm, concentrated energy. 5. Moderate alcohol use is good for the body Although it is not an alcoholic ferment.

such as wine or beer, this beverage does contain traces of alcohol. These naturally occurring low alcohol concentrations can raise and stress lower emotions of wellbeing.[1,2,10,11]

• Butterfly pea

(*Clitoria ternatea*) is a herbal remedy that has been traditionally used to help

- anxiety ○ stress ○ Insomnia ○ depression [12]
- some Potential Benefits
- calming effects □ stress relief □ Improved sleep □ mood enhancement

Table 1: The main chemicals [13,14,15]

Flavonoids	Alkaloids	Glycosides
Kaempferol	Clitorine	Clitoroside
Quercetin	Clitoridine	
Rutin		

This compounds flavonoids, alkaloids, glycosides interact with the brain's neurotransmitters, such as:-

■ GABA (gamma-Aminobutyric acid) :- Flavonoids and alkaloids in blood pressure may enhance GABA activity, promoting relaxation and reducing anxiety. [18]

■ serotonin: - Flavonoids may influence serotonin levels, helping to regulate mood and reduce anxiety. [19,20]

■ Dopamine: - Alkaloids in blood pressure may affect Dopamine levels, which can help reduce stress and anxiety.

Chemicals work [12,13,16,17]

Kaempferol: -
 » reducing stress hormones » anxiety reducing

(interacting with gaba , exhibits axiomatic)
 Quercetin: -
 » reduce oxidative stress » calm anxiety and stress » Improve sleep quality » reduce inflammation in the brain

Rutin:- same as Quercetin

Clitorine:-
 » reduce stress hormone like – cortisol » help mitigate oxidative stress

Clitoroside:-
 » support focus » Improve mood and emotional regulation

Primary ingredients included in the beverage

There are currently no clinical trials carried out with the same level of rigor as those for pharmaceutical medications. The process of fermentation, which yields nourishment in a living form.

amino acids

The SCOBY is a complete protein in and of itself since it includes all nine of the required amino acids (along with those that are not thought to be essential). The greatest levels were reached after 21 days of fermentation in a black tea substrate (* indicates the essential compounds).

Table (2) amino acids

Alanine	Proline	Histidine*	Lysine*	Tyrosine
Arginine	Glutamic acid	Isoleucine*	Methionine *	Valine*
Aspartic acid	Glycine	Leucine*	Phenylalanine*	
Cysteine	Serine	Threonine*	Tryptophan *	

Organic acids

Table (3) Acids found in drink

Acetic acid	Capric (decanoic)	Citric acid	Hyaluronic acid
Benzoic acid	Caproic (hexanoic)	Gluconic acid	Lactic acid
Butyric acid	Glucuronic acid	Nucleic acid	Usnic acid

4-ethylphenol, Ethyl acetate, Phenethyl alcohol, Antioxidants

Vitamin C

Table (4) B vitamins

B1–Thiamine
B2-riboflavin

B6-pyridoxine
B12-cobalamine or cyanocobalamin

Table (5) Enzyme: -

Amylase	Hexokinases	Phytases
Carbohydrase	Invertase	Protease
Catalase	Lipase	Sucrase

Naturally occurring sugar

Fructose, glucose

Caffeine (theine)

Theobromine and theophylline

Metabolites of glucuronic acid

COMPOSITION: -

Ingredient: -

Butterfly pea, tea, sugar

Equipment used for the experiment

includes a fermenter vessel, tea balls, a strainer, a long-handled spoon, a cloth cover, a thermometer, a heating pad, a filter, a funnel, a digital balance, a PH strip or PH meter, and a measuring cylinder.

Before starting the formulation

make sure your workspace and all of your packaging materials are clean and sanitized. It is advised that you wear protective clothes and gloves.

The following are the steps to make a healthy drink:-

Steep tea: Bring water to a boil and let tea steep for ten or more minutes.

sugar: Mix sugar into the heated water.

Strain tea: Remove the tea or strain the loose tea while straining.

Incorporate SCOBY: Incorporate a newly-fermented SCOBY (Symbiotic Culture of Bacteria and Yeast) into the jar along with some starter

Cover and incubate: a cloth or coffee filter over the jar and fasten it with a rubber band to start the incubation process. Incubate for seven to thirty days at room temperature. It will get more vinegary and less sweet the longer it ferments.

Taste: Your brew is ready to be sampled after roughly five days.

Bottle: Pour the beverage into an airtight bottle to preserve the carbonation.

Add Herb: Butterfly pea extract is a good option. You can also make your own SCOBY by mixing water, sugar, black or green tea, and premade Healthy drink [1,21]

Fig. (1) Healthy drink

It All Start With The Scoby:-

Fig. (2) SCOBY BACTERIA [29]

SCOBY (Symbiotic Culture of Bacteria and Yeast):

• What is a SCOBY?

A cellulose-based, gelatinous biofilm known as a SCOBY is home to a variety of microorganisms, including yeast and bacteria. It's a live, breathing organism that ferments tea and sugar into a beverage. [21, 23]

Make-up: Typically, a SCOBY includes: *Komagataeibacter xylinum*, also known as *Acetobacter xylinum*, is the main bacteria in a SCOBY and is responsible for producing large amounts of cellulose.

Its purposes are to:

- Ferment tea and sugar to make a drink
- Transforms caffeine into advantageous molecules
- Generates acids, antioxidants, and other advantageous elements
- Serves as a natural filter, drawing pollutants out of the liquid

Care and upkeep:

- Keep the SCOBY out of direct sunlight and other contaminants
- Feed it sweet tea on a regular basis
- Store it in a clean, dry location.

Interesting Information

- A SCOBY can multiply and create additional layers, so you can share it with others
- The SCOBY has been used for generations in traditional Chinese medicine
- It can be used to ferment other liquids, such as ginger beer

Remember, it is important to handle the SCOBY with clean hands and equipment to preserve its health and avoid infection.

- **Avoid-** Steer clear of any dehydrated, chilled, or frozen SCOBY.

Characteristics of a quality Culture:-

- Bacterial mat is between ¼ and ½ inch thick
- yeast strands are present
- color is white and brown
- the starter liquid is strong
- the Bacterial mat is hardy:- tightly between thumb and forefinger [1,21,22,23]

Quality cultures have the following characteristics:

- Yeast strands are present
- The color is a combination of white and brown
- The bacterial mat is between ¼ and ½ inch thick
- A robust starting liquid and a resilient bacterial mat: Holding firmly with the thumb and forefinger [1,21,22, 23]

- **Tea, sugar, and water are additional ingredients.**

Brew There are only four main ingredients in this drink: tea, sugar, water, and the SCOBY together with its beginning liquid.

Selection of Tea: Tea varieties include: black, white, green, oolong, and pu-erh.

Tea Prerequisites: - Premium tea bags or leaves Caffeine (essential for SCOBY growth) must be present in tea. Antioxidants and polyphenols are desirable ingredients in tea.

Mixtures of tea: A combination of black and green tea: balanced profile of flavors and antioxidants Spiced and fragrant combination of tea Blended tea with fruit infusion: tangy and revitalizing

How to Make Tea:

INGREDIENTS: 4–6 tea bags or 4–6 teaspoons of loose tea leaves One gallon of cold, chlorine-free water a single cup sugar

BREWING: Transfer the tea to a saucepan, bowl, or other heat-resistant vessel. Pour 4 cups of barely boiling water over the tea. After letting it steep for ten to fifteen minutes, take off the used tea leaves. After adding the sugar and stirring until it dissolves fully, pour in the remaining water in the hot tea.[30]

Tea Boiling Temperature 68–85°F (20–30°C) is the ideal temperature range for SCOBY development. – Steer clear of temperatures below 50°F (10°C) or above 90°F (32°C). The pH level of tea

The ideal pH range : 2.5 to 3.5 is needed for SCOBY development.

Tips and Considerations:

Use filtered water to avoid impurities:-Steer clear of tea that has flavorings or preservatives added; Try a variety of teas to select the one with the flavor profile you like most; and Store tea in a cold, dry area to maintain antioxidants and flavor.[1, 3]

Sugar:- turbinado sugar, white sugar, and evaporated cane juice [30]

Water sources :- include spring water, bottled water, well water, and municipal tap water [30]

Suitable Herbs And Tisanes For Blending

To optimize the potential health benefits of herbs that have been predigested through fermentation, try experimenting with different herbal infusions. [13, 15,17]

Use Butterfly Pea :-

Use Butterfly Pea (*clitoria ternatea*) is a herbal remedy.

Butterfly Pea (*Clitoria ternatea*) is a fascinating herb with various uses.

Overview:

- **Scientific name:** *Clitoria ternatea*

- **Common names:** Butterfly Pea, Blue Pea, Asian Pigeonwings

- **Native to:** Tropical Asia, Southeast Asia, and Africa

Traditional Uses:

1. Ayurvedic medicine: Memory, cognitive function, and stress relief

Fig. (3) Butterfly Pea

2. Traditional Chinese medicine: Fever reduction, detoxification, and anti-inflammatory

3. Southeast Asian cuisine: Food coloring, tea, and herbal remedies [26,27]

Culinary Uses:

1. Tea: Blue-colored tea with a floral, slightly sweet flavor

2. Food coloring: Natural dye for desserts, drinks, and cosmetics

3. Herbal infusions: Blended with other herbs for medicinal benefits

Nutritional Content:

1. Vitamins: C, B1, B2, B3, B5

2. Minerals: Calcium, iron, magnesium, potassium

3. Antocyanins (powerful antioxidants)

4. Flavonoids (antioxidant and anti-inflammatory) [24,25]

Concentration:

Children (4-12 years):

• 0.5-1% (w/v) butterfly pea flower extraction

Adults (13+ years):

• 1-3% (w/v) butterfly pea flower extract

• Pregnant/Breastfeeding Women:

• 0.5-1% (w/v) butterfly pea flower extract

(Avoid giving to children under 4 years old) [12,14,16]

Precautions:

1. Pregnancy and breastfeeding: Consult a healthcare professional

2. Allergies: Rare, but possible allergic reactions

3. Interactions: May interact with certain medications (e.g., blood thinners) [27,26]

extraction procedure for Butterfly Pea (*Clitoria ternatea*):

Materials:

- Dried Butterfly Pea flowers or leaves

- Water

- Cheesecloth or a coffee filter

- A clean container for the extract

Procedure:

1. ratio: one part Butterfly Pea to ten parts water (10g Butterfly Pea to 100ml water, for example).

2. Steeping: In a sanitized container, mix water and Butterfly Pea. Depending on the intensity you want, steep for 30 minutes to 2 hours.

3. Strain: Transfer the mixture to a different container by passing it through cheesecloth or a coffee filter. Throw away the solids.

4. Filter: If desired, run the liquid through one more filter to get rid of any leftover contaminants.

5. Concentrate: If desired, concentrate the extract by freeze-drying, spray-drying, or evaporation

Some variations include:

- Cold infusion: Soak the Butterfly Pea for a long time (e.g., 8–12 hours) in cold water.

- Hot infusion: Steep the Butterfly Pea for a shorter amount of time (10–30 minutes) in hot water (90–100°C, for example).

- Repeated extraction: To maximize the yield of bioactive chemicals, repeat the extraction procedure many times

Fig. (4) Butterfly Pea extraction [28]

Notes:

- To maximize the extraction of particular bioactive chemicals, adjust the temperature, steeping period, and ratio.
- To avoid contamination and guarantee the extract's quality, use distilled water.
- To maintain its quality, keep the extract in a dark, clean container.

Advantages Of Healthy Drink

Physical Health Benefits:

1. Probiotics: Supports gut health and immunity
2. Antioxidants: Protects against cell damage and inflammation
3. Anti-inflammatory: Reduces joint pain and inflammation
4. Detoxification: Aids in removing toxins from the body
5. Boosts energy: Increases vitality and mental clarity
6. Weight loss: Supports metabolism and weight management
7. Improves digestion: Relieves bloating, constipation, and IBS symptoms

Mental Health Benefits:

1. Reduces stress and anxiety
2. Improves mood and cognitive function
3. Enhances focus and concentration
4. Promotes relaxation and calmness
5. Supports mental clarity and memory

Immune System Benefits:

1. Boosts immune system function
2. Protects against infections and diseases

3. Supports autoimmune disease management
4. Reduces inflammation and oxidative stress

Skin and Hair Benefits:

1. Improves skin elasticity and hydration
2. Reduces acne and inflammation
3. Promotes healthy hair growth
4. Enhances skin radiance and glow

Other Benefits:

1. Supports cancer prevention
2. May help manage diabetes
3. Supports liver health
4. May improve joint health
5. Supports healthy gut bacteria [1,30]

DISADVANTAGES

1. Contamination risk: Improper brewing or handling can lead to contamination.
2. Allergic reactions: Some individuals may be allergic to kombucha or its ingredients.
3. Interactions with medications: May interact with blood thinners, diabetes medications, and immunosuppressants.
4. Acidic pH: May erode tooth enamel or irritate digestive issues.
5. Caffeine content: May exacerbate caffeine sensitivity [1]

CONCLUSION

A fermented tea drink, offers a range of potential health benefits, including improved gut health, boosted immunity, and enhanced mental clarity. With its rich probiotic and antioxidant content, drink has become a popular beverage among health enthusiasts. [30]

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